

Content curation to build and share content hubs for knowledge management and information literacies

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Abstract

Amount of information, through scientific published papers and social media networks is more and more overwhelming and the term “infobesity” was coined for information overload. There is also now abundance of tools to find information. However, access to specific information by end-users (either professionals, researchers, educators, students...) remains a challenge for many. Information professionals, such as librarians and institutes can offer help building personalized resources and contents. Strategic intelligence, science and technical watch are helping companies with specific methods and software. But individual researchers are more and more in charge of their own information search but have not received training during their students’ years. Content curation emerged as a « new » concept some years ago and numerous tools are now available on the internet but their usage seems more focused on marketing purposes than on information, knowledge management and education. From our personal experience and from other curators, we evaluated in a research action project the possibilities and hindrances of this activity for open knowledge and information management, and the opportunities in scholarly communication and information literacies education. We analysed successful topics on Scoop.it in terms of audience in various domains such as Biological Sciences (Immunology, Virology, Entomology..), Geography, Education, etc.. Advantages of using a content curation tool such as Scoop.it to collect and aggregate relevant information of interest for professionals, teachers, students... are present at the different levels of information management process. Finding information relies mainly on crawling engines, but also when browsing. More and more relevant ones also come from general social networks (Twitter, LinkedIn...) and from scientific or common interest networks, even on the same curation tool. Selecting information as well as commenting, elevating, tagging depends on the curator activity. Illustrating can be offered by the tool or modified by the curator. He can also create and publish scoops. Information is then posted as a virtual attractive Web open magazine. It can be shared further on various social networks, through e-mail and/or newsletters. After archiving, an inside search engine allows retrieval, months or

years after posting. If advantage versus artificial intelligence is the human added value of curation, it is also the main limit requiring regular and persistent activity. Another limit, surprising from educators, is the willingness to share information. Content Curation allows building specific relevant resources content hubs for content discovery and distribution. It can be used by professionals in various fields of interest, researchers, and laypeople willing to follow their topics of interest, keep abreast of information, building leadership and open new connections of knowledge through serendipitous encounters. Educational usage helps students and trainees surfing the wave of information and mastering health and information literacies. It can be used in hybrid and blended active learning, stimulating curiosity. Their content hub can be used as a portfolio, and help them build a personal learning network for their future life-long learning.

Keywords: Content Curation, Content Hubs, Scoop.it, Knowledge management, Information literacy

Introduction

Information overload is becoming more and more an hindrance for end-users in working, learning and teaching, even if it is not considered as such by students (Bawden, 2020). Theoretically, there is abundance of tools to access information, even surabundance, but many end-users (students, professionals, researchers, educators, ...) do not master the specificity and diversity of them and rely mainly on general search tools such as Google (Duddy, 2009). The problem becomes a challenge in working environments and corporate settings and even more for health-related professions due to the sensitivity of topics and to the spreading of fake news (Scantlebury, 2017).

Strategic intelligence, science and technical watch have been helping companies with specific methods and software for industrial, and economical requirements. Information professionals in libraries developed many innovations to introduce and teach their customers mastering softwares and their practices. Many new tools are developed and proposed by start-ups and publishers, more and more with artificial intelligence to help accessing information through computers and mobiles. In universities and hospitals, paradoxically, individual researchers are more and more in charge of their own information search but have seldomly received any specific training during their students' years.

Content curation emerged as a « new » concept some years ago and numerous tools are now available on the internet but their usage seems yet more focused on marketing purposes than on information, knowledge management and education (Cherrstrom, 2020, Dale, 2015).

Methods

We developed a research action project to analyze and confront our personal experience and activities of other persistent (more than one year) curators, with a large activity and wide audiences, using the Scoop.it tool. We focused on content hubs in areas of common interest such as biological sciences, health and medicine as well as education. Methods implied a qualitative analysis of the usage of the tool by curators.

The main topics covered in the study to evaluate potentials of the tool were the following : Immunology <https://www.scoop.it/u/gilbertfaure>; Virology <https://www.scoop.it/topic/virusworld>; Entomology <https://www.scoop.it/topic/entomonews>; Geography <https://www.scoop.it/topic/geography-education>; Education and

Learning <https://www.scoop.it/topic/tools-for-learners>, <https://www.scoop.it/topic/21st-centurytools-for-teaching-people-and-learners> as well as many other topics.

We also experienced and implemented content curation as a tool for teaching and learning in subgroups of learners and trainees. They were asked to build personal content hubs on topics of interest: college students on geography (Faure, 2018), medical students as a practical initiation to methods of clinical medical and surgical research and discovery (Faure, 2022) of medical knowledge as well as media and health information literacy. They were assessed on choice of topic, activity of curation, quality and relevance of selection, tagging and commenting.

Findings

Content hubs is the term coined for such collection of information and web resources, preferred to the word of databases. It has been proposed in library workplaces (Fritz, 2018). Content curation tools can be used by information professionals but also by non-professionals, such as teachers and allows them to gather information resources from the web and express their competencies and interests.

The practical advantages of using a content curation tool such as Scoop.it to collect, aggregate and share relevant information of interest by/for professionals, teachers, students... are present at the different levels of information management process:

Finding information relies mainly on crawling engines, but also when browsing. More and more, relevant ones also come from general social networks (Twitter, LinkedIn...) and from scientific or common interest networks, even on the same curation tool. It can be found by curators through searching on classical existing databases.

Selecting information as well as commenting, elevating, tagging depends on the curator interests and activity.

Curation can be done individually, but also as a group, allowing to share the amount of work, becoming obviously sometimes overwhelming. Illustrating can be offered by the tool, modified or chosen by the curator. He can also create and publish scoops with personal images or PPTs, for instance through Slideshare. In some plans, documents can also be posted and shared. Information is then posted as a virtual attractive Web open magazine. Topics can remain private in confidential environments, but most curators share freely and openly the results of their activity.

It can be shared further on various social networks chosen by curators such as Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook..., through individual e-mails and/or via newsletters in special plans.

After archiving, an inside search engine allows retrieval, months or years after posting. This is a big asset in research helping curators and users to find information posted a long time before, but forgotten. It uses keywords and/or tags and also natural language.

Discussion

Content curation allows teachers and researchers experienced in some topics to remain abreast of the evolution of knowledge in their discipline and fields of research. It enlarges the information covered by classical databases, widens the domain and accelerates access to recent information through diverse sources. It adds serendipity opportunities to

researchers, coming from the diversity of resources available. Sharing on their topic viewed and followed by others colleagues and students helps building leadership in their areas, and joining new networks and communities of interest. Teachers and students can be involved in new ways of learning, flipped, blended or hybrid. Practice of content curation helps them to discover and then master information, information tools and techniques. Learning by reading and writing can be assessed through material collected and commented, and stimulating curiosity (Aguilar-Pena, 2022, Quarchioni, 2022).

The human added value of curation is the main advantage adding individual, competent and curious minds to automatic search and crawling engines. Indeed, such tools collect much informational noise requiring either elaborated search processes or human selection by specialists. The selection is the first activity of human curators. It should be completed by tagging keywords, helping find again relevant material collected months or years before. Curators should also comment on the quality and relevance of information they post and elaborate on potential connections between information.

Apart from technical evolution and policy of the developers of the curation tools, human involvement is also the main limit requiring regular and persistent activity. Indeed, from data collected on the tool, many naive curators begin this activity but quickly stop after a few days or weeks. On the other hand, persistent and active curators some after years, for personal reasons (such as retirement and/or health problems) do not pursue their activity even deleting their production from the website. Another internal limit, surprising from educators, is their willingness to share the information they can find during their web-surfing.

Conclusion

We evaluated the possibilities and limits of a regular activity of content curation for open knowledge and information management, and the opportunities in scholarly communication and information literacies education (Antonio, 2014, Antonio, 2013, Kortelainen, 2016). Content curation allows building specific relevant resources content hubs for content discovery and distribution. It can be used by professionals, researchers, and laypeople willing to follow their topics of interest, keep abreast of information, building leadership and open new connections of knowledge through serendipitous encounters (Reviglio, 2019). Educational usage helps students and trainees surfing the wave of information and mastering health and information literacies. It can be used in hybrid and blended active learning, stimulating curiosity. Such content hubs can be used as portfolio by master/PhD students and young researchers and help them build a personal learning network for their future life-long learning.

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